

Life in a Box: Have Smartphones Become our New Identity?

*Personal documents stored on smart devices and the
question of privacy.*

by Alex Weissel

Do you have a smartphone? The answer is most probably yes. Some of us have two, three or more. Mobile devices have become standard even in the most remote and underdeveloped areas of the world. Estimates say that in 2023 there were almost 7 billion smartphones on earth, covering an astounding 85% of human population. On the other hand, only 74% of humanity had access to clean water and barely 50% to basic medical care. It would seem our priorities have evolved in odd directions.

Aside from serving as a camera, social media gateway and communication device, smartphone is increasingly becoming an essential part of our identity, and not just figuratively. In a day and age when information plays the key socio-economic role, primarily digital information that is, we are left to wonder: what are the implications of having one's entire life stored in a disposable piece of electronics, connected to the entire world, that can be accessed at any given time, by essentially anyone?

Smartphones are quickly taking over the role that a humble wallet played for centuries, not only as cash repository, but a keeper of our most important documents.

Contactless payments, as well as numerous payment apps have become the norm. Currency in physical form is slowly but surely being outed, as are classic debit and credit cards. With the introduction of fully digital currencies — a process which is well under way — states and governments (not banks) will have direct insight and control over one's individual funds. In other words, every single payment you make will be noted and stored in a government-run cloud, as will every income. On the top of that, should some entity decide to limit or totally cut your access to own capital, it could be done with a single click. Smartphones are quickly taking over the role that a humble wallet played for centuries, not only as cash repository, but a keeper of our most important documents.

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Our personal documents; IDs, passports, insurance cards and driver's licenses are still being issued in physical form. But this is about to change. Pilot programs such as the European Digital Identity are already being implemented, meaning that all private data is to be stored in smartphones and clouds alike: birth certificates, personal addresses, travel destinations, GPS locations, medical records, financial statements, credit ratings... the lot. One could argue that all this information is already kept somewhere, and that the issued documents merely represent an authorised copy. That is true, yet, a physical document, unlike a smartphone, cannot be accessed remotely, hacked or locked. Should it get lost or stolen, the potential for misuse is rather limited. On the other hand, a missing device, with every aspect of one's life in digital form, can be multiplied, distributed and sold without limits. As we've witnessed so many times, any computer and any database can be accessed. Just think of your existing digital footprint acquired through simple web browsing, and how many data brokers are managing it at this very moment.

What About Privacy?

Many years ago, when travel controls were being introduced and tightened, I had a conversation with a colleague on the topic. She essentially concluded that none of this presents an issue for her, considering she "has nothing to hide". I heard such arguments over and over again, from governments, corporations and individuals alike. Apparently, we've come to the point where discretion and hiding have

acquired the same meaning. The idea of keeping one's personal information private is treated as insincerity, or worse, conspiracy. This, of course, is nothing new. Totalitarian regimes have exercised such logic for centuries. The irony and contradiction, however, imply that while we're constantly reassured of our freedoms and rights, here in the Developed world, giving them away is becoming the new normal, all in the name of keeping those same freedoms and rights.

Can you stop digitalization? No. It's a trend set on a solid path. But then, not all digitalization is bad. Many of its aspects remain beneficial. Nonetheless, should you want to keep your identity, privacy, and ultimately humanity, stay physical as long as possible.

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